

Identification of emerging Brucella species: new threats for human and animals (IDEMBRU)

**D-JRP17-WP1.Del3 -
Development of flowcharts and
related tools facilitating
investigation and decision-
making of emerging *Brucella*
outbreaks**

Work package 1

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IZSAM, WBVR

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D-JRP17-WP1.DEL3

Development of a flowchart and related tools facilitating investigation and decision-making of emerging *Brucella* outbreaks

Background

Emerging animal reservoirs of different *Brucella* species have been identified with the potential to spillover to domestic animals and humans, such as *B. melitensis* biovar 3 in Alpine ibex (Mick et al., 2014), *B. suis* biovar 2 in wild boars, hares and roe deer (Mailles et al., 2017; Sting et al., 2014), *B. ceti* in marine mammals (Whatmore et al., 2008), and *B. canis* in pets and humans (Hofer et al., 2012; Kaden et al., 2014; Lucero et al., 2010). These facts show that new studies and resources to improve preparedness and response to potential brucellosis outbreaks in reservoirs, that are not subject to statutory control or surveillance strategies, are needed. Identification of new animal and human cases is crucial to better evaluate new zoonotic threats and to develop more robust systems of detection and identification.

A major goal in IDEMBRU project was to develop a collaborative toolkit (WP6) to improve National and International networks to identify emerging *Brucella* species and reservoirs. The toolkit integrates specific characteristics of *Brucella* species, and comprises a collection of optimised and harmonised methods, guidelines, tracking systems including emerging *Brucella* and flowcharts on outbreak investigations, to (1) describe an outbreak with a minimal dataset; (2) define harmonized investigation strategies for the identification of emerging *Brucella* species and reservoirs; and (3) provide the resources and flowcharts necessary to properly characterise strains with harmonised methods integrating classical phenotypic, genomic and proteomic approaches and assessment of behaviour in virulence models.

Given the recent cases of *B. canis* infection in several EU Countries, and considering its zoonotic potential and the absence of diagnostic and management tools, the WP leaders and deputies decided to elaborate two complementary parts of the toolkit: one specific for *B. canis* diagnostic and outbreak management (I), and one focusing on detection and characterisation of emerging *Brucella* species and/or reservoirs (II).

The final toolkit will be available on the websites of the One Health EJP, ANSES and EFSA, as well as at the Reference Laboratories webpages as a support tool.

In this report we will briefly describe both toolboxes.

I. BRUCELLA CANIS TOOLBOX: DIAGNOSTIC FLOWCHARTS FOR KENNEL OUTBREAK CONFIRMATION and FOR OUTBREAK MANAGEMENT

In the presence of a kennel dog with symptoms compatible with brucellosis a quick laboratory confirmation should be made, as the disease will spread to other animals quickly after it enters into the facilities.

The *B. canis* toolbox will include guidelines and standard operating procedures (SOPs) for the collection of samples and first-line serological tests for *B. canis* specific antibodies, including agglutination tests (RSAT, 2ME-RSAT, TAT

and 2ME-TAT), complement fixation test (CFT), agar gel immunodiffusion test (AGID); enzyme-linked immunoassay (ELISA), and lateral flow immunoassay (LFIA).

Furthermore, the toolbox will include flowcharts for decision-making upon negative or positive serological results in dogs. In the presence of a suspicious dog (individual or kennel dog) laboratory confirmation should be made efficiently, and intra kennel measures should be taken to avoid spreadness of the disease into other animals, namely isolation of the suspicious dog.

Guidelines for the detection of the bacterium is highlighted with accurate descriptions of currently available detection methods, such as bacteriology, molecular methods, or MALDI-TOF. If the *Brucella* infection is confirmed, the first step is to raise awareness of people who handle and interact with animals (owners, breeders, kennel workers) about canine brucellosis, namely it's aetiology (*B. canis*, but sometimes *B. melitensis*, *B. suis*, or *B. abortus*), zoonotic risk, routes of transmission and clinical signs.

Also, strategies for biosecurity measures will be integrated to help contain spreadness of the disease. Epidemiological investigation aiming the identification of dogs and people contacting with the infected animals should start as soon as possible, and all dogs epidemiologically linked to the infected dogs must be tested, as well as previously positive animals, keeping separated the positive ones.

II. DETECTION AND CHARACTERISATION OF EMERGING *BRUCELLA* SPECIES AND/OR RESERVOIRS

The toolbox dedicated to the detection and characterisation of emerging *Brucella* species and/or reservoirs is composed of reference databases, epidemiological questionnaires, harmonised protocols, guidance on interpretation, tracking systems, and flowcharts on confirmation of atypical *Brucella*-like isolates, and brucellae in non-preferred host. Again, the detection of the bacterium is emphasised with accurate descriptions of currently available detection methods (eg. RT-PCR, bacteriology), and by new methods such as high throughput methods, such as NGS, proteomics (MALDI-TOF), antibiotic sensitivity tests, motility or in vitro infection models. These new characterisation approaches include functional markers such as, virulence, resistance to antibiotics, and development of in vitro infection models to understand virulence and zoonotic potential.

Moreover, the toolkit will contain flowcharts and related tools to facilitate investigation and decision-making regarding emerging *Brucella* outbreaks, from different sources, under various epidemiological contexts in terms of natural landscape, livestock demographics and wildlife.